

ROLE AND IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS - A STUDY

V. Indira Mudiraj

Research Scholar, Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana

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Abstract:

English is popularly known as a Global language. It was completely influenced by several other languages in due course. Since its evolution, its impact on every individual regardless of the age, gender, creed, culture, tradition. Now, the technology and social media are leaving its own mark on English. The role of technology in our life is quite surprising. Its effect on the way we communicate has changed the English language forever mainly on written communication. The advent of technology brought revolutionary changes in language usage. People get the feel of using very simple language so as to communicate their ideas, feelings more clearly and effectively.

It has evolved into a new dimension with the advent of the use of internet. The primary aim of any language is to communicate. The process of communication is overwhelmingly transforming day-by-day. Communication was widely considered a successful process when it was done in synchronic manner. Lately technology has revolutionized the process of communication that even asynchronous approach is widely and more rapidly becoming an apt tool for learners or communicators. As people become good communicators it indicates that they are also good learners.

The social networking providers are flooding the internet with so many options at hand for the users and it has been increasing rapidly day by day. Carol A. Chapelle, in her article: Technology and Second Language Acquisition says that, "Computer technology provides learners with new and varied options for language learning through interactive tasks delivered through CD-ROMs, Web pages and Communications software on the Internet".

Social media networks such as Facebook (FB), WhatsApp and SMS have made in-roads into all spheres of human life bringing forth a revolution in mobile communication networking and in sending short messages services (SMS). Writing on the social media networks requires creativity and skill. This is to maximize the use of the text message page, reduce the cost of sending the message and also belong by using 'text-speak' which is often associated with informal usage. The worry is how this is affecting the usage of Nigerian students' performance in written English. After examined the prevalence of miss pelt words, use of slangs, abbreviations and looked at social media in relation to its impact on students' written English. From FB, SMS and WhatsApp as well as expressions and spellings taken from secondary school students' essay writing were analyzed Finding indicated that social media language is gradually and steadily encroaching students' writing. Students should also be given drills in spelling, use of grammar and punctuation.

Key Words: Technology, Revolutionary, Social Media, Language, Written English, ICT, SMS, Interactive.

Social networks are becoming an integral part of people's lives. Students are spending much time on social media and are considered the largest category that uses such application. This study tries to explore the influence of social media use, and especially Facebook, on high school students' performance. The study used the GPA of students in four courses and their responses regarding the use of social media. Statistical analysis is used to infer this relationship and its implications. Results indicated a support of this study aim and the relationship between the different dimensions of Facebook influence on students with respect to the time spent on the Internet and Facebook specifically. Conclusions and future work are stated at the end.

Social media has gained incredible popularity over the past few years as an open source of information and knowledge sharing platform .Educational institutions are using social media space to interact with young minds. We are seeing educators leveraging the potential of social media technologies to enhance the overall teaching-learning process.

The emerging role of social media in teaching-learning process cannot be ignored. It not only provides students access to useful information but also connects them with learning groups and other educational systems that make their overall learning process more interesting and engaging.

"The media (social media platforms, newspapers, radio/telecommunication services) on one hand are providing adequate information about safety measures to control the infection, but on the other hand, excessive

description of COVID-19 related news in all social media platforms/ telecommunication platforms is creating a sense of panic among the vulnerable individuals.” (Grover, et al., 2020)

Social media is the fastest growing web application in the 21st century. The diverse applications of Social Media like Wikis, video streaming and applications, and social networks make it the phenomenon of the century. Facebook counted users topped all social media applications with over 955 million users in 2013, followed by Twitter with 500 million users (www.thecountriesof.com). Such huge user base is comparable to countries, which indicates the importance of such applications. The age distribution of Facebook users is concentrated on the younger categories where 300 million users are 18-24 years old, and 120 million users are between 13-17 years old (www.quintly.com). The same source indicated a nearly equal distribution of users between males and females.

This phenomenon is made usable by means of the internet and the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) as well as the advent of smart phones. There are many social media platforms. Some readily available ones include Facebook, Skype, Twitter, MySpace, WhatsApp, 2go, SMS. Activities on social media are for socializing, getting and sharing information, discussing assignments and projects, debates, chats, collaborating and networking. According to Freeman (2016), social media can be a useful tool for educational activities when approached in the right way.

Social platforms like Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube and Instagram are being used by almost everyone. These social channels are all about collaborating, networking, sharing and generating knowledge and content – something which is of great value in the context of education. Few ways in which social media is helping professors, students and universities are mentioned below, take a look. One of its disadvantages is its impact on the way secondary students spell words and write. Secondly, is the negative influence on students' time management, study behaviour and copying of wrong concepts. For Paul & Gelish, (2011) the use of mobile phones for sending short messages and accessing social media may and may not result in students' lower academic performance.

However, from classroom observation, social media language is infiltrating students' formal writing exercises and impacting it negatively. This supports Selwyn's (2009) assertion that Facebook use must be seen as identity politics of being a student rather than enhancing students' engagement with formal studies. During classroom interaction with students, one finds that most of the students write using incorrect spelling, grammar and punctuation marks. Many use abbreviations profusely, while others have formed the habit of using text speak. This affects the structure of sentences used as well as their spellings. This in turn does not argue well for students' vocabulary acquisition. Again, based on classroom observation of happenings in Mopamuro Local Government Area of Kogi State, lack of teachers (qualified or not), coupled with large student population sometimes, makes detailed checking of errors difficult. They only gloss over students' work or ask that fellow students do the marking. This may result in some students being unaware of the difference between formal and informal writing. To compound the problem, majority of the students struggle with grammar, concord, meaning and comprehension.

Benefits of Using Social Media in Teaching and Learning: How Teachers & Educators can Use Social Media to Enhance Teaching-Learning Process:

With the advent of internet technology, Social media has become an integral of every student's life. Through social networks, it is easier and convenient to exchange information, communicate with each other and stay connected. Teachers and students can use social platforms to stay connected to each other and can use it for educational purpose.

Social networks are empowering students and educational institutions with opportunities to improve teaching-learning process. Slide Share, Quora and Research Gate etc. are helping students by providing online tutorials. These platforms offer valuable resource material for enriching knowledge base. Social media is also a medium where students can establish beneficial connections for their careers. As an educational institution, it is crucial to be active in many social platforms possible, this helps create better student engagement strategies and makes learning more interactive and inclusive. Professors can use their Twitter or Facebook handles or even messaging services such as WhatsApp to hold live sessions, offer extended support to students thereby enhancing the scope of learning beyond classroom. They can organize discussions related to their subjects or class assignments on social media platforms. Social media therefore helps both teachers and students to remain connected off campus. Faculty can create groups using social media where useful information can be accessed by all. It is a good platform for sharing ideas. They can use hash tags to increase outreach of their academic posts and view submissions by students to check engagement level. One of the main reasons behind teachers adapting to social media in and out of the classrooms is that they can do personal branding using social media. This helps in creating a name for them in the academic fraternity. Face book, Twitter, various blogging sites and YouTube are some of the social channels where professors can market their expertise. These platforms are highly popular among students and hence can help in establishing high reputation. After all, who wouldn't want that his / her work should get recognized! Teaching fraternity is therefore acknowledging the impact of social media on personal and professional lives. Social media is increasingly becoming popular in building relationships outside the classroom setting. It is helping drive admissions and strengthen public relations of the Institute. Students' welfare department in colleges is taking help of social media to engage students by addressing their grievances. It is further being used to showcase life at campus and build strong alumni networks. Social media properties are being used in learning for the purpose of convenient communication with other students and potentially with others outside the class. You can connect with industry experts through Facebook live sessions. To get started using social media in teaching, consider what you want to achieve. Do you wish to help students in their assignments beyond teaching hours.

7 Ways Social Media can Benefit Professors and Students in Teaching and Learning:

Revolutionary changes in technology have open various opportunities to enhance teaching as well as learning experiences of students. The world of education has completely transformed ever since the internet and smart phone technologies came to existence. Rising popularity and usefulness of social networking websites has led educators to explore their potential use in education. Educational institutions have realized the capability of social media to improve collaboration and active learning. Social media is paving way for a new age learning which is personalized and customized to suit the need of every learner. In an increasingly interconnected world, professional networks and connections have become key to one's success and future growth.

In this context social media has a lot to offer to the educational community. Here are some of the direct benefits of social media usage for the academic world:

1. Collaborative Learning:

Social Media as a Learning Platform for Students

On social media, students exchange lot of information. So, why not use this platform to encourage collaborative learning. In fact, several institutions globally are encouraging students to forge international partnerships using social media for taking up some project assignments.

By doing this, they get engaged with each other and learn how to manage projects and coordinate with teams sitting globally along with cross cultural sensitivities. Similarly, the use of social media has made it easier and faster to interact with peers or teachers about class-related topics. Use of social media also familiarizes students with a new work culture of managing work through online engagements which is very important in today's business environment. It teaches them how to develop a strong online presence by improving their communication skills.

2. Information Sharing by Students:

Students are continuously hooked on to the internet through their smart phones and hence rapidly transmit information to their connections. Apart from just sharing views and opinions they also exchange lot of valuable information. This information is a lot more than just interesting videos or snapshots and cover useful stuff related to their studies. They exchange helpful information for classes and examinations.

3. Social Media Marketing for Educators:

For educational institutions, social media is a great marketing tool to reach out to the prospective students. This new media has led education professionals to build a strong marketing strategy to increase brand awareness. Colleges all over the world are extensively carrying out social media strategies to tap students. They are connecting with experts on topics via social media. Through blogging and Slide Share, teachers are soon establishing themselves as experts in particular fields and subjects. Students gain useful content by following these experts online. This empowers institutions and establishes its brand equity in the academic world. Academic Institutions are communicating with students via YouTube and Facebook. These channels can be used to communicate campus news, make announcements and provide students with useful information. This builds engagement between the College and students which helps in building trust by addressing many student related issues through community interactions. As part of their marketing strategy, Institutions can share supportive and useful posts that can connect their audience in a positive way. You can initiate hash tags on social media to engage students in online discussions that are helpful. Video is a prominent tool in social media trends and is very effective in communicating your messages. You can use it to share useful and interesting stories that can inspire students and help them prepare for the challenges ahead.

4. Helps to Foster Research:

Social media offers collaborative opportunities to foster research initiatives. It is one of the best platforms to extract secondary data. You can conduct survey pools to gather sampling and find out opinions of general people and other experts on a particular subject.

Social media can help academic researchers compile and produce useful content by working on collaborative assignments and projects.

5. Continue Teaching from Anywhere and Everywhere:

Sometimes, it is difficult to address queries of students during classroom sessions. This makes it further difficult for students to clear their doubts. However, professors can take advantage of social media technology to extend teaching hours beyond classroom. They can set up Facebook Live sessions or Twitter discussions to cover uncleared doubts of their students. As a matter of fact, professors can allocate dedicated time slots for online discussions to answer any question or to work with a student. Through Facebook sessions, Faculty can connect with large audiences at one go which otherwise is not possible in one class.

6. Take Advantage of Blogs to create Virtual Library:

Setting up a personal blog or website gives professors a lot of freedom to build intellectual credibility. They can upload their academic work and other important lectures and videos that will allow students to take relevant inputs as reference material for their studies.

7. Let Students Learn from Social Networking:

Social media offers great learning opportunities through social networking. Students can be encouraged to build networks to support professional help in career.

Similarly, Professors can also connect with the students and help them identify suitable job openings and find relevant connections for their future profession.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

As social media networks advance in education systems, many helpful and beneficial tools will emerge that can make learning a more enriching experience. Students today are intimately involved with social media at every stage. If you're missing out on the usage of social media you are pushing away a lot of potential audience. Using it in educational institutions can prove to be a very effective measure. The benefits of social media for academic entities are many. The above are just a few, to begin with. Social media sites offer great opportunities for communication between peers and teachers. Using social media, teachers can improve the involvement of their students in studies and education, improve technological ability, provide a great sense of collaboration in the classroom and build good communication skills of students.

The Positive and Negative Impact of Social Media on Students Academic Achievement Social media tools makes connection easier and faster as it expands our universe. In addition, it deepens learning by creating a wider range of options to explore by both the students and instructors which is done at their own convenience on the choice on what methodology is best suited in the teaching-learning process. Some of the options include:

online teaching- learning which is becoming more popular and accessible anywhere in the world through internet connection. O'keeffe and Clake-pearson (2011), in their study discovered that students can also share, solve and discuss class activities, assignments and group projects on social media within or outside the school premises. It is further propped by Arquero and Esteban, (2013) and Selwyn, (2007) whose suppositions were that social media has unquestionably created innovative prospects to engage students in secondary education as they are remarkably effective at connecting people thereby expediting the exchange of information. In spite the positive aspects which shows the importance and effect of social media on students' academic achievement, Davies and Cranston (2008); Okeeffe and Clake-Pearson (2011), highlighted some of the menaces related with social media which include immoral activities such as: identity theft and fake contacts, online sexual harassment, inapt advertising, cyber bullying, sexting, privacy trepidations, social media online addiction, loneliness and depression. These immoral activities make students lose the factual aspect of the natural human communication skills as they spend more time on frivolities which will thus affect them negatively.

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